

Figure 2. Predicted sperm motility across pH and osmolality gradients based on a generalized additive model (GAM) with a linear \times smooth interaction. Observed (left) and predicted (right) sperm motility across pH and osmolality gradients for *Rana muscosa*. Observed values represent mean percent motility within discrete pH and osmolality bins. Predicted values were generated from a generalized additive model (GAM) with a linear \times smooth tensor interaction (pH \times s(Osm)), using scaled inputs and converted to percent motility. The model predicts highest motility (yellow) at low pH (6.5–7.0) and moderate to high osmolality (75–100 mOsm/kg). However, observed values show a more restricted pattern, with peak motility (73%) only at pH 7.0 and osmolality 50–100 mOsm/kg, and lower motility across all other conditions. Both panels use a viridis color palette to facilitate direct comparison.